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Summary of Implemented Indicators and Measures

SURVEY RESULTS AND DATA ON
**IMPROVING GENDER EQUALITY
IN RESEARCH ORGANISATIONS**

**SCIENCE
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'Summary of Implemented Indicators and Measures: Survey Results and Data on Improving Gender Equality in Research Organisations'

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Summary of Implemented Indicators and Measures

SURVEY RESULTS AND DATA ON IMPROVING GENDER EQUALITY IN RESEARCH ORGANISATIONS

INTRODUCTION

This document complements the ‘Practical Guide to Improving Gender Equality in Research Organisations’, authored by the Science Europe Working Group on Gender and Diversity. It provides the qualitative and quantitative background data on which parts of the Practical Guide are based.

The Practical Guide can be found at <http://scieur.org/gender-guide>.

The Working Group on Gender and Diversity launched a survey in the autumn of 2015 to measure the implementation of gender equality measures within the Science Europe Member Organisations. Thirty responses to the survey were received in total, representing 35 out of 47 organisations.^{1, 2}

The results of the survey are briefly analysed and both the original survey and question responses are included.

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IMPORTANT DISCLAIMER: The authors of this document recognise that the terms ‘male’ and ‘female’ are biological terms and differ from the terms that a person may use to describe their gender. The terms ‘man’ and ‘woman’ are commonly used for this purpose, but some people have a gender identity that is in between or beyond these terms, or that fluctuates between them; they may also consider themselves to have no gender at all. In this publication, the authors have chosen not to use the terms ‘male’ and ‘female’ and have opted to use ‘men’ and ‘women’, sometimes to the detriment of strict grammatical correctness.

1 Research Councils UK responded on behalf of the seven individual UK research councils. A separate response from the Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council is therefore not included in the following results. Additional information in their response was taken into account for production of the Practical Guide, however.

2 One duplicate response is also not included in the following results. The 28 remaining respondents in this document represent 35 Member Organisations.

How to Monitor Gender Equality

Summary of Implemented Indicators

Since basic data on gender distribution is crucial for monitoring gender equality, it was important to get an overview on what types of indicators Member Organisations were using.

The survey questions were divided across seven sections aimed specifically at Research Funding Organisations (RFOs), Research Performing Organisations (RPOs), or both types of organisation.

1. Statistics on the gender distribution in the national 'pool of researchers'	RFOs and RPOs
2. Data for gender equality monitoring of research funding organisations	RFOs
3. Data on the recruitment of researchers/academic teachers (open to external applications)	RPOs
4. Data on the (internal) promotion of researchers or academic teaching staff in the organisation	RPOs
5. Data on the recruitment and/or promotion boards and decision-making bodies in the organisation	RPOs
6. Data on the total number of researchers or academic teaching staff in the organisation	RPOs
7. Concluding questions	RFOs and RPOs

Respondents had the possibility to make optional comments on each question in order to provide more detailed answers. While these were taken into account when analysing the results, they are not reproduced here in order to retain the anonymity of the results.

Key Findings

Strategic goals

The main conclusion drawn from the survey results is that the respondents do collect gender-disaggregated data in a lot of areas, with some differences and exceptions on several points. Almost all respondents publish their data on the distribution of women and men in a yearly publication.

Most countries do provide national statistics on the percentage share of women and men in the researcher pool,² and most are broken down by academic position, scientific field, and age. From the 24 respondents in countries with available statistics, 18 said that they actually used those statistics – leaving just six respondents that have these statistics available, but who do not make use of them.³

In addition, the majority of respondents collect disaggregated data on the number of applications, as well as on successful applications from women and men⁴ by funding scheme and scientific field. However, only just over half of the respondents monitor whether the average size of grants given to women and men differ.

Prizes

The Working Group on Gender and Diversity also took a closer look at prizes or awards given to excellent researchers. Roughly half of RFOs (14 out of 24) award prizes. However, less than half of them collect disaggregated data and even less have an estimate for the number of women and men researchers in their target group for the prize. Collecting these data could help put the number of successful candidates in relation to the pool of potential winners, and thus evaluate the funding rates for women and men.

Reviewers and Decision-making Bodies

Around three quarters of the respondents collect disaggregated data on the number of women and men reviewers, but not all of them break it down by funding scheme or scientific field. Just ten of them reported that they record the gender of the chair of these review panels.

3 See Question 2. One organisation answered with "no", four organisations did not know.

4 Unless noted otherwise, these numbers refer only to RFOs, as the number of RPOs that responded to the survey was very small.

5 See Questions 3 and 4: 23 Yes, 2 No (RFOs). See also Question 5: 14 Yes, 11 No (RFOs).

Survey Questions and Results

Questions and text in this section are those from the original survey sent to Science Europe Member Organisations. Some minor modifications were made for consistency and clarity.

1. Please indicate whether your organisation is primarily a Research Funding Organisation (RFO), a Research Performing Organisation (RPO) or fulfils both missions.

Part 1 Gender Equality Monitoring Performed in Science Europe Member Organisations

Basic data on sex distribution is crucial for the monitoring of gender equality. An important objective of the Working Group on Gender and Diversity is to identify useful indicators of gender equality and to recommend to the Science Europe Governing Board a common and practical set of indicators on gender equality for all Member Organisations.

The recommended indicators should aid Member Organisations in monitoring their gender equality status and progress and when necessary inform their actions.

With this survey, we want to find out what data the Member Organisations of Science Europe (both Research Funding Organisations and Research Performing Organisations) already collect.

Section 1 Statistics on the gender distribution in the national 'pool of researchers' RFOs and RPOs

To see whether women and men apply equally often for research funding (RFOs) or for research or academic teaching positions (RPOs) respectively, it is useful to compare the percentage share of women and men among applicants with the percentage share of women and men in the national 'pool of researchers' (assuming that the national researchers are in a clear majority among the applicants). As an example: the national pool of researchers for a basic research council can often be estimated to be the researchers or academic teaching staff with a PhD at the higher education institutions and at the institutes for basic research. Further, the pool of researchers for junior researchers grants can often be estimated as the researchers or academic teaching staff below a certain age with a PhD; or preferably as the researchers or academic teaching staff with a PhD not older than a certain number of years.

2. Are national statistics available on the percentage share of women and men in the researcher pool?

- 2.1. If yes, does your organisation use national statistics for the analysis of gender equality?

- 2.2. If yes, are the national statistics broken down by academic position?

2.3. If yes, are the national statistics broken down by scientific field?

2.4. If yes, are the national statistics broken down by age?

Section 2 Data for gender equality monitoring of Research Funding Organisations RFOs only

Two commonly used indicators for gender equality in research funding are the **share of applications** from women and men among all applications, and the **success rate** for women and men. The success rate is the share of granted applications among all applications from women and men.

3. Does your organisation collect disaggregated data on the number of applications from women and men?

3.1. If yes, are the data on the number of applications broken down by funding scheme?

3.2. If yes, are the data on the number of applications broken down by scientific field?

4. Does your organisation collect disaggregated data on the number of successful applications from women and men?

4.1. If yes, are the data on the number of successful applications broken down by funding scheme?

4.2. If yes, are the data on the number of successful applications broken down by scientific field?

5. Do you collect disaggregated data on the average size of grants given to women and men?

5.1. If yes, are the data on the average size of grant broken down by funding scheme?

5.2. If yes, are the data on the average size of grant broken down by scientific field?

6. Some Research Funding Organisations give prizes or awards to excellent scientists. Does your organisation give such prizes or rewards?

6.1. A useful gender equality indicator is the share of women and men among prize winners. If yes, does your organisation collect disaggregated data on the number of women and men winning prizes or awards?

6.2. If yes, does your organisation have disaggregated estimates of the total number of women and men in the group of 'national potential winners', i.e. those eligible to receive a prize or award?

7. Two commonly used indicators for gender equality are the proportion of women among reviewers and the proportion of women on decision-making bodies (research funding decisions). Does your organisation collect disaggregated data on the number of women and men reviewers?

7.1. If yes, are the data on the number of women and men reviewers broken down by funding scheme?

7.2. If yes, are the data on the number of women and men reviewers broken down by scientific field?

8. Does your organisation collect disaggregated data on the number of women and men among chairs of review panels?

9. Does your organisation collect disaggregated data on the number of women and men on decision-making bodies?

9.1. If yes, are the data on the number of women and men on decision-making bodies broken down by scientific field?

Section 3 Data on the recruitment of researchers/academic teachers (open to external applications) RPOs only

Two commonly used indicators for gender equality are the **share of applications** from women and men among all applications, and the **success rate** for women and men. The success rate is the share of successful applications among all applications from women and men.

10. Does your organisation collect disaggregated data on the number of applications from women and men?

10.1. If yes, are the data on the number of applications broken down by academic position?

10.2. If yes, are the data on the number of applications broken down by scientific field?

10.3. If yes, are the data on the number of applications broken down by permanent vs. temporary position?

10.4. If yes, are the data on the number of applications broken down by full-time or part-time position?

11. Does your organisation collect disaggregated data on the number of successful applications from women and men?

11.1. If yes, are the data on the number of successful applications broken down by academic position?

11.2. If yes, are the data on the number of successful applications broken down by scientific field?

11.3. If yes, are the data on the number of successful applications broken down by permanent vs. temporary position?

11.4. If yes, are the data on the number of successful applications broken down by full-time or part-time position?

Section 4 Data on the (internal) promotion of researchers or academic teaching staff in the organisation

RPOs only

Some organisations have a system for internal promotion and careers, in some organisations scientists must personally apply for promotion, while in others promotion occurs after internal review procedures or with seniority.

12. Does your organisation have a system for internal promotion?

Yes	6	
No	2	
No Answer	–	

12.1. If yes, does your organisation require that researchers apply for promotion?

Yes	5	
No	1	

12.1.1. If yes, does your organisation collect disaggregated data on the number of applications for promotion from women and men?

Yes	4	
No	1	

12.1.1.1. If yes, are the data on the number of applications broken down by academic position?

12.1.1.2. If yes, are the data on the number of applications broken down by scientific field?

12.2. If yes, does your organisation collect disaggregated data on the number of promotions of women and men?

Yes	5	
No	–	

12.2.1. If yes, are the data on the number of promotions broken down by academic position?

12.2.2. If yes, are the data on the number of promotions broken down by scientific field?

13. Some Research Performing Organisations give important internal prizes or awards to excellent scientists, such as the Gold, Silver and Bronze Medals of the CNRS, France. Does your organisation give such prizes or awards?

Yes	5	
No	3	
No Answer	-	

- 13.1. A useful gender equality indicator is the share of women and men among prize winners. If yes, does your organisation collect disaggregated data on the number of women and men winning prizes or awards?

- 13.2. If yes, does your organisation have disaggregated estimates of the total number of women and men in the group of 'potential winners', i.e. of those potentially eligible to receive a prize or award?

Section 5 Data on the recruitment and/or promotion boards and decision-making bodies in the organisation RPOs only

Two commonly used indicators for gender equality in a Research Performing Organisation are the **proportion of women on recruitment and/or promotion boards** and the **proportion of women on decision-making bodies**.

14. Does your organisation collect disaggregated data on the number of women and men on recruitment and/or promotion boards?

Yes	5	
No	3	
No Answer	-	

- 14.1. If yes, are the data on the recruitment and/or promotion boards broken down by scientific field?

- 14.2. If yes, does your organisation collect disaggregated data on the number of women and men who are chairs of recruitment and/or promotion boards?

- 12 15. Does your organisation collect disaggregated data on the number of women and men on decision-making bodies of your organisation?

Yes	8	
No	-	
No Answer	-	

- 15.1. If yes, are the data on the number of women and men on decision-making bodies broken down by scientific field?

Section 6 Data on the total number of researchers or academic teaching staff in the organisation RPOs only

A commonly used indicator is the **share of women among researchers and/or academic teaching staff** in the organisation. The share of women in a certain academic position can also be used to compare with the share of women among applications for promotion to the position on the next level.

16. Does your organisation collect disaggregated data on the number of women and men among researchers or academic teaching staff in your organisation?

Yes	8	
No	-	
No Answer	-	

- 16.1. If yes, are the data on the number of researchers or academic teaching staff broken down by academic position?

- 16.2. If yes, are the data on the number of researchers or academic teaching staff broken down by scientific field?

- 16.3. If yes, are the data on the number of researchers or academic teaching staff broken down by permanent or temporary position?

- 16.4. If yes, are the data on the number of researchers or academic teaching staff broken down by full-time or part-time position?

17. Does your organisation mention gender equality in its statutes, its strategic plan, instructions or any similar documents?

18. In what year did your organisation start to collect disaggregated data on the number of women and men?

19. How often does your organisation collect the disaggregated data on the number of women and men?

20. Does your organisation have any goals or targets connected to the gender equality data it collects, or does it use the data in some other strategic way?

20.1. If yes, are there any (mandatory) actions taken if the goals or targets are not met?

21. Does your organisation publicly report data on the distribution of men and women in your organisation's activities in an annual report or other publication available to the management or the general public?

Yes	26	
No	2	
No Answer	-	

22. Does your organisation collect other types of data or calculate other indicators concerning gender equality, rather than those mentioned above?

Yes	10	
No	17	
No Answer	1	

How to Avoid Unconscious Bias in Peer-review Processes

Summary of Implemented Measures

The second part of the survey addressed the MOs' discussions of potential unconscious (or implicit) biases in evaluation processes. These are the most important results from this part of the survey:

1. The importance of unconscious bias as a factor in peer review has been acknowledged in more than half of responding MOs.
2. Gender was named most often as a topic in discussions on unconscious bias, followed by age and ethnic background.
3. Many responding MOs do take actions to minimise the occurrence of unconscious bias. However, internal discussions to raise awareness have not been conducted systematically.

A large number of respondents (21 out of 29 – Question 25) stated that unconscious bias might come into play during discussions by review panels. Many of these organisations also believe that unconscious bias might occur while evaluating CVs, during interviews, and when evaluating letters of recommendation.

Many respondents (20 out of 29 – Question 26) claim to take action to minimise potential unconscious bias, however not all have taken any action to raise awareness internally. Of these 20 respondents, five actually provide guidelines for reviewers, training for reviewers, and compose gender-balanced panels. The composition of gender-balanced panels is the most often mentioned action to minimise bias.

However, as recent studies show, the composition of evaluation panels is in itself not necessarily an effective way to minimise bias (Van der Lee & Ellemers, 2015; Schiffbaenker & van den Besselaar, 2016). Nevertheless, gender-balanced panels do prove to be of critical importance in showcasing role models and helping applicants to identify with panel members.

Survey Questions and Results

Questions and text in this section are those from the original survey sent to Science Europe Member Organisations. Some minor modifications were made for consistency and clarity.

Part 2 Unconscious Bias in Peer-review Processes

Extensive research demonstrates how implicit biases and social stereotypes affect evaluation in the peer-review process. For example, a CV headed by a female name is evaluated differently than the identical male CV by both male and female reviewers or applicants with names representative of a given country are more likely to be hired than those with names associated with minority ethnic backgrounds. These biases are one of the factors leading to the underrepresentation of groups such as women in research.

23. Has the problem of unconscious bias in peer-review and evaluation procedures been discussed in your organisation?

Yes	16	
No	11	
No Answer	1	

24. If bias in evaluation processes is discussed, which factor(s) is/are considered to play a role?

Gender	16	
Age	12	
Ethnicity	7	
Disability	2	
Discipline	1	
Nationality	1	
Reputation	1	
Socio-economic background	1	
Affiliation	1	

25. At which points of the evaluation process in your organisation do you think an unconscious bias could come into play?

In panel discussions	20	
In CV evaluation	17	
In interviews	13	
In letters of recommendation	10	
In the way the peer-review process is organised	2	
In the selection of peer reviews	1	
In the way the call is advertised	1	
In review reports	1	
In co-optation procedures	1	
In the assessment of the independence of the researcher	1	
In everything	1	

26. Does your organisation take actions to minimise potential unconscious bias in your evaluation system?

Yes	19	
No	8	
No Answer	1	

26.1. If yes, in what way?

Gender-balanced panels	16	
Guidelines for reviewers and/or panel members	11	
Training for reviewers and/or panel members	9	
Training for research council staff and decision-making bodies	2	
Gender-blinding applications	1	
Specific committee put in place	1	
Evaluation of review process	1	
Awareness-raising	1	
Quality control of decisions	1	

List of Respondents

The following organisations responded to this survey:

Country	Name of Organisation	Acronym	Organisation Type
Austria	Austrian Science Fund	FWF	RFO
Belgium	Fund for Scientific Research	F.R.S.-FNRS	RFO and RPO
Belgium	Research Foundation Flanders	FWO	RFO
Czech Republic	Czech Science Foundation	GAČR	RFO
Denmark	Danish Council for Independent Research	DFF	RFO
Denmark	Danish National Research Foundation	DG	RFO
Estonia	Estonian Research Council	ETAG	RFO
Finland	Academy of Finland	AKA	RFO
France	French National Research Agency	ANR	RFO
France	French National Institute for Agricultural Research	INRA	RPO
France	National Centre for Scientific Research	CNRS	RFO and RPO
Germany	Max Planck Society	MPG	RPO
Germany	German Research Foundation	DFG	RFO
Germany	Leibniz Association	Leibniz	RPO
Iceland	Iceland Centre for Research	Rannís	RFO
Ireland	Science Foundation Ireland	SFI	RFO
Ireland	Irish Research Council	IRC	RFO
Ireland	Health Research Board	HRB	RFO
Italy	National Institute for Nuclear Physics	INFN	RFO and RPO
The Netherlands	Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research	NWO	RFO and RPO
Norway	Research Council of Norway	RCN	RFO
Poland	National Science Centre	NCN	RFO
Slovenia	Slovenian Research Agency	ARRS	RFO
Spain	Spanish National Research Council	CSIC	RPO
Sweden	Swedish Research Council for Environment, Agricultural Science and Spatial Planning	FORMAS	RFO
Sweden	Swedish Research Council	VR	RFO
Switzerland	Swiss National Science Foundation	SNSF	RFO
United Kingdom	Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council ^A	BBSRC	RFO
United Kingdom	Research Councils UK	RCUK	RFO

A See Footnote 1, page 3.

Science Europe is a non-profit organisation based in Brussels representing major Research Funding and Research Performing Organisations across Europe.

More information on its mission and activities is provided at www.scienceeurope.org.

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